

Bank Aceh Syariah: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

**Dita Nurmawanadilah, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria
Dewi**

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Bank Aceh Syariah using a qualitative approach, which takes the form of library research and VOSviewer bibliometrics. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Bank Aceh Syariah " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank Aceh Syariah based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 4 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Bank Aceh Syariah, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; and (4) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Aceh Syariah, both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Bank Aceh Syariah; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

The Aceh regional policy to convert from conventional banking to sharia banking can be implemented in other regions. This conversion provides positive results on the level of bankruptcy risk in running the banking business model. Aceh is one of the areas where the level of public compliance with Islamic law is very high, so that the implementation of sharia in banking can run well. However, some people do not fully understand Islamic banking. Therefore, some people still consider Islamic banks to be the same as conventional banks. This makes the people of Aceh have a choice between sharia banks and conventional banks (Yuliusdharma et al., 2022).

In 2016, PT Bank Aceh converted from a conventional system to a sharia system. The change in the name of Bank Aceh to PT Bank Aceh was approved by Bank Indonesia Governor Decree No. 12/61/KEP.GBI/2010 dated 29 September 2010. Finally, now it has become PT Bank Aceh Syariah with pure sharia practices in accordance with the Decree of the Board of Commissioners of the Financial Services Authority Number KEP-44/D.03/2016 dated 1 September 2016, which refers to Financial Services Authority Regulation Number 64 POJK.03/2016 (Pambuko & Pramesti, 2020).

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Bank Aceh Syariah on Sharia Financial Inclusion using library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Bank Aceh Syariah, so that

it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Aceh Syariah, both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Aceh Sharia Bank approved by the Financial Services Authority (OJK) on September 19 2016 with the stipulation of operational permits for conversion to the sharia system. This is based on the Decree of the OJK Board of Commissioners Number KEP44/D.03/2016 dated 1 September 2016 concerning the Granting of Permits to Change Business Activities of Conventional Commercial Banks to become Sharia Commercial Banks PT Bank Aceh which was submitted directly by the OJK Board of Commissioners in Banda Aceh. The inauguration of the Conventional Aceh Bank which was converted into a sharia system-based Aceh Bank has caused pros and cons to arise among the community (Hartika, 2021).

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and compile the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study (Jalilah, 2021) (Syaripuddin, 2020).

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications (Dubyna et al., 2022).

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-

understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is Bank Aceh Syariah. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Bank Aceh Syariah. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Bank Aceh Syariah " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank Aceh Syariah based on the journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Bank Aceh Syariah

Search results of scientific publications regarding Bank Aceh Syariah during the period 2009 to 2022 show an increase in publications every year, especially in the last five years. We found a total of 69 article titles originating from accredited national and international journals. Even in 2021, the number of publications reached 18 articles. So, the average scientific publication about Bank Aceh Syariah is more than six articles per year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Bank Aceh Syariah by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2009	1	2018	10
2013	2	2019	12
2014	2	2020	17
2015	1	2021	18
2016	1	2022	1
2017	4		
Total = 69			

Source : Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there are 10 affiliates/institutions that publish the most research articles about Bank Aceh Syariah. From this table, it can be seen that

the civil law student scientific journal is the journal publishing institution that publishes the most research results regarding Bank Aceh Syariah, namely six articles.

Table 2. Ranking of 10 institutions and journals publishing scientific publications at Bank Aceh Syariah

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Amount Publication
Student Scientific Journal for Civil Law, Faculty of Law, Syiah Kuala University	6
Share: Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance, Economics and Business, Ar-Raniry State Islamic University	5
Scientific Journal of Accounting Economics Students, Accounting Department of Economics and Business Faculty Syiah Kuala University	4
Jihbiz: Global Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance, Sharia Banking Study Program FEBI UIN Ar-Raniry / Journal of Sharia Economics, Master of Sharia Economics Study Program UIN Ar-Raniry	3
E-Mabis: Journal of Management and Business Economics Faculty of Economics and Business, Malikussaleh University / Ekonis: Journal of Economics and Business, Lhokseumawe State Polytechnic / Accounting and Finance Journal, Department of Accounting, Faculty of Economics & Business / KITA EMT Journal, KITA Institute / Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics and Business Students, Faculty of Islamic Economics and Business, Ar-Raniry State Islamic University Banda Aceh	2

Source : Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

The most productive researcher discussing Bank Aceh Syariah is Budianto from Teuku Umar University, who wrote two journal articles. Meanwhile, other authors only wrote one journal article.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Bank Aceh Syariah.

The results of this search were obtained from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garb a) which were exported into RIS (research information systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSViewer. Here are the results:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps surrounding Bank Aceh Syariah

Data was processed using VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

The results of the co-word network map of research developments regarding Bank Aceh Syariah are divided into 8 clusters and 116 topics, namely :

- Cluster 1. Red consists of 21 topics, namely : article, banda aceh, commitment, data analysis, effect, employee, employee performance, influence, job insecurity, job satisfaction, work, organization, organizational commitment, organizational culture, organizational support, path analysis, person, turnover intention, work environment, work motivation.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 20 topics, namely : bank, Bank Aceh Syariah, bank health, change, customer loyalty, data, difference, fund, good corporate governance, interview, Islamic bank, management, mechanism, murabaha financing, observation, bank side, principle, risk, study.
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 18 topics, namely : assets, capital, conversion, earnings, effectiveness, fdr, financial performance, gcg, npf, profitability, ratio, return, risk profile, roa, roe, significance probability, tbk, tcount.
- Cluster 4. Yellow color consists of 16 topics, namely : asset ratio, bi rate, deposit ratio, determination, factor, financing, financing ratio, murabahah, murabahah financing, murabahah financing decision, musarakah financing, object, rate, regression coefficient, research, rfr.
- Cluster 5. The color purple consists of 12 topics, namely : bireuen regency, convenience, customer, micro entrepreneur, number, perception, perception, profit, rahn, respondent, significant influence.
- Cluster 6. Light blue consists of 12 topics, namely : Aceh bank, correlation value, dps, human resource account, measurement, organizational structure, primary data, questionnaire, religiosity, reporting, source, third party fund.

- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 11 topic items, namely : amount, coefficient, increase, percent, percent, profit sharing, quality, saving, service, value, variable.
- Cluster 8. The color brown consists of 3 topics, namely : agricultural risk, determinant, product knowledge.
- Cluster 9. The color pink consists of 3 topics, namely : information system, significant effect, user.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Financial Performance of Bank Aceh Syariah

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 12 topics related to the financial performance of Bank Aceh Syariah, namely:

First, the Murabahah financing repayment pattern. The following are the general steps in the Murabahah financing repayment pattern: (1)Financing Application: The customer submits a financing application to the bank, explaining the purpose and details of the financing requested (2)Assessment and Approval: The Bank will evaluate the financing application and conduct a feasibility analysis. If approved, the bank and customer will sign a Murabahah financing agreement (3)Asset Purchase: The bank will purchase the assets desired by the customer at a cash price. These assets will belong to the bank (4)Sales to Customers: The bank sells assets to customers at a price that includes the cash purchase price plus the bank's markup or profit. The selling price will be divided into installments that must be paid by the customer (5)Installment Payments: Customers will pay installments according to the agreed schedule. Installments can be paid monthly or according to the period specified in the agreement (6)Full Repayment: The customer must pay off the financing in full after all installments have been paid in accordance with the agreement (Yahya, 2020).

Second, the influence of the BI rate on the percentage of profit sharing from Musyarakah financing. The influence of the BI Rate on the percentage of profit sharing from Musyarakah financing at Bank Aceh Syariah can be explained as follows: (1)Influence on Interest Rates: Bank Indonesia's policy regarding the BI Rate can influence interest rates for bank financing, including Musyarakah-based financing at Bank Aceh Syariah. When the BI Rate rises, interest rates on commercial bank loans tend to rise as well, including interest rates on Musyarakah financing at Bank Aceh Syariah. On the other hand, when the BI Rate falls, bank loan interest rates tend to decrease, and this could have an impact on profit sharing rates in Musyarakah financing (2)Investment Risk: Musyarakah Financing involves two or more parties sharing the risks and profits of a project or business. If the BI Rate increases, commercial bank interest rates also increase, which may cause investors or partners in Musyarakah financing to demand higher profit sharing to compensate for the higher investment risk due to higher interest rates (3)Demand for Financing: BI Rate can also influence demand for financing from the public and companies. If the BI Rate increases, higher interest rates could make people more careful in applying for financing. Conversely, when the BI Rate falls, demand for financing tends to increase because lower interest rates make financing more affordable (4)Bank Aceh Syariah Policy: Although the BI Rate is the reference, Bank Aceh Syariah also has an internal policy regarding the determination of profit sharing rates in Musyarakah financing. Profit sharing rates can be determined based on

other factors such as project risk, expected profits, and market conditions. Banks must also comply with sharia principles in determining Musyarakah-based financing schemes (Raihana, 2020).

Third, determining Murabahah profit margins. The following are the general steps usually involved in determining Murabahah profit margins in Islamic banks: (1)Risk Analysis: Bank Aceh Syariah will conduct a risk analysis to determine the appropriate profit margin amount. This includes assessing business risk, market risk, liquidity risk and other relevant risk factors (2)Operational Costs: The Bank will calculate operational costs related to Murabahah transactions, including procurement costs, administrative costs, and other costs related to the sales process (3)Funding Costs: Bank Aceh Syariah will also consider the funding costs they face. This involves capital costs, funding costs, and other costs associated with the bank's funding sources (4)Market and Competition: Banks will consider competition in the market and compare their profit margins with other Islamic banks to ensure that they remain competitive (5)Reasonable Profit: Banks will also consider the level of profit that is reasonable for their business. This includes a fair return on investment and keeping the bank financially sustainable. After considering the above factors, Bank Aceh Syariah will determine the Murabahah profit margin in accordance with sharia principles and applicable regulatory requirements. This margin will be applied to the selling price of goods purchased by the bank and then resold to customers with a markup that reflects the bank's profits. It is important to note that the determination of Murabahah profit margins in Islamic banks can also be influenced by fatwas and guidelines from regulatory bodies and competent sharia authorities in the region. Therefore, practices and policies may vary between different Islamic banks and may also change over time (Malahayati, 2020).

Fourth, accounting for Qardhul Hasan's financing. The following are the general steps in accounting for Qardhul Hasan financing : (1)Submitting an Application: The party who needs financing submits an application to the bank to obtain Qardhul Hasan (2)Evaluation: The Bank will evaluate the application to determine the financing needs and eligibility of the recipient. In sharia principles, giving Qardhul Hasan must be based on goodwill (Hasan)and the recipient's ability to return the funds (3)Approval: After evaluation, if the application is declared successful, the bank will approve the granting of Qardhul Hasan and determine the amount and term of financing (4)Disbursement of Funds: After approval, the bank will disburse the funds according to the agreement to the recipient (5)Accounting Records: On the accounting side, funds provided as Qardhul Hasan must be recorded as part of the bank's receivables by recording the financing in the bank's accounting system (6)Repayment: The recipient of the financing is expected to return the funds according to the agreement, without additional interest or fees (7)Recording Repayment: When the recipient pays off the financing, the bank will record the receipt in the accounting system as a deduction from the bank's receivables (Khairani, 2019).

Fifth, implementation of Murabahah/commercial financing. The following are the general steps taken by sharia banks in implementing murabahah financing: (1)Financing Application: Applicants who are potential customers will submit an application for murabahah financing to Bank Aceh Syariah. The application will include information about the business or investment to be funded, the amount of funds required, and the financing period (2)Feasibility Evaluation: Bank Aceh Syariah will evaluate the feasibility of the

applicant and the project to be funded. This process includes credit and risk analysis, as well as ensuring that the applicant meets the requirements set by the bank (3)Price Determination: After the applicant is declared eligible, the bank and the applicant will determine the selling price of the goods or assets that will be purchased by the bank and then resold to the applicant at a mutually agreed price. The selling price usually includes acquisition costs and the bank's profit margin (4)Murabahah Agreement: After the selling price is determined, the bank and the applicant will sign a murabahah contract, which is an agreement for the purchase and resale of goods or assets according to the agreed price. In a murabahah contract, the bank will disclose the acquisition costs and profits that will be obtained as part of the financing (5)Financing: After the murabahah contract is signed, the bank will purchase the goods or assets desired by the applicant from the seller. Then, the bank will sell the goods back to the applicant at a previously agreed price, but with payment in installments according to the agreement (6)Repayment: The applicant will pay the installments in accordance with the agreement stipulated in the murabahah contract until the financing has been repaid (R. Rahmawati, 2019).

Sixth, resolving financing problems. Several general steps that sharia banks can take to resolve problematic financing include: (1)Problem identification: Banks need to precisely identify financing that is experiencing problems, compile a list of problematic financing, and analyze the root causes (2)Financing evaluation: After identifying problematic financing, the bank must carry out a credit evaluation by examining the debtor's profile, the final cause of the problematic financing, and the debtor's financial condition (3)Communication with debtors: Banks need to communicate with debtors actively to find joint solutions and understand the debtor's financial situation. This can include discussing the problems faced by the debtor and finding the best solution for both parties (4)Financing restructuring: If the debtor faces temporary financial problems, the bank may consider restructuring the financing by providing a longer term, reducing the interest rate, or rearranging payment terms to better suit the debtor's condition (5)Conditional repayment: If the debtor is still able to pay, the bank can offer a conditional repayment scheme, where the financing can be repaid in several stages according to the debtor's ability (6)Deliberative settlement : Banks can try to resolve problematic financing through deliberation with the debtor to reach an agreement that benefits both parties (7)Sale or transfer of assets: In some cases, banks may consider selling or transferring non-performing financing to third parties (8)Legal resolution: If the above steps are unsuccessful, the bank may consider legal action to resolve problematic financing, for example, through an auction process or filing a claim in court (Antoni, 2018).

Seventh, implementation of profit sharing/ revenue sharing. The following are the general steps taken in implementing profit sharing at Bank Aceh Syariah: (1)Identification of Financing: Customers who wish to obtain financing from Bank Aceh Syariah must submit an application and submit information regarding the project or business to be funded. The bank will evaluate the proposal to ensure the halalness and potential of the business (2)Risk Assessment: Bank Aceh Syariah will carry out a risk analysis of the project or business to be funded. This involves assessing the feasibility of the business, legal aspects, finances, and compliance with sharia principles. The bank will also evaluate the potential returns and associated risks (3)Determination of Profit Sharing: After the risk assessment is complete, Bank Aceh Syariah and the customer will reach an agreement regarding the

proportion of profit sharing. This proportion can be adjusted based on the expected profits and risks involved. Profit sharing can be set as a fixed percentage or based on the distribution of net profit (4)Financing and Use of Funds: If an agreement is reached, Bank Aceh Syariah will provide financing to the customer. These funds can be used by customers to start or develop their business in accordance with the agreed goals (5)Monitoring and Evaluation: Bank Aceh Syariah will continue to monitor and evaluate the progress of funded businesses. This aims to ensure that financing is used correctly and in accordance with sharia principles. The bank will also ensure compliance with profit sharing in accordance with the initial agreement (6)Profit Sharing: After the project or business produces profits, Bank Aceh Syariah and the customer will share the results according to the initial agreement. The determined profit sharing proportion will be used as the basis for calculating profit sharing. This profit sharing can be done periodically, for example every month or every year (Razali, 2018).

Eighth, the influence of costs and measurement of the value of Human Resources on Human Resources accounting reporting. In general, here are some influences that the cost and measurement of HR value may have on HR accounting reporting at a sharia bank: (1)HR costs: HR costs include salaries, allowances, training and other benefits provided to bank employees. The effect in accounting reporting is as an expense that must be recorded in the financial statements. Higher HR costs can reduce bank net profits and affect other financial performance indicators (2)Measuring the value of HR: Measuring the value of HR is a way to assess the quality and contribution of employees to bank performance. This measurement includes an assessment of employee performance, development potential and competency. If the bank has a good HR value measurement system, it can help in making strategic decisions related to human resources, such as salary policies, training programs and promotions (3)HR accounting reporting: HR accounting reporting involves disclosing financial and non-financial information related to HR in financial reports. This includes information about HR costs, incentive policies, HR development programs, and performance appraisals. Transparent and comprehensive reporting can provide stakeholders (such as shareholders, regulators and the public) better insight into HR management and bank performance (Purba, 2017).

Ninth, the influence of Financing to Asset Ratio, Rate of Return of Financing Ratio, Financing to Deposit Ratio on the decision to provide Murabahah financing. It is important to remember that each bank's financing policy can be different and can be influenced by a number of broader factors, including the bank's internal policies, market conditions and applicable regulations. However, let's discuss the three financial ratios mentioned: (1)Financing to Asset Ratio/ FAR: This ratio measures how much financing is provided by the bank in relation to the total assets it owns. The higher the FAR, the greater the proportion of bank assets used to provide financing. If the FAR is high, banks may be more careful in providing additional financing, including Murabahah financing, to avoid potential liquidity risks (2)Rate of Return of Financing Ratio/ RRF: RRF measures the rate of return on financing provided by banks. This ratio is relevant in the context of Murabahah financing because the financing is based on a buying and selling mechanism with a price markup. The bank will consider the RRF to assess the profitability of the financing that has been provided. The higher the RRF, the better it is from the bank's perspective (3)Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR: FDR measures how much financing is provided by the bank in relation to the total deposits it has. This

ratio shows the bank's dependence on third party funds to provide financing. If FDR is high, banks may need to think about alternative funding sources or adjust the volume of financing provided (Fahmi, 2017).

Tenth, the influence (intellectual capital, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Non Performing Financing/NPF, Return on Equity//ROE, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Allowance for Impairment Losses/CKPN, Mudharabah financing, Operational Costs on Operating Income/BOPO) on financial performance. The following is a brief explanation of each of these factors: (1) Intellectual Capital : Intellectual Capital refers to the value of the knowledge, skills and experience possessed by an organization. At Bank Aceh Syariah, this intellectual strength can increase innovation, operational efficiency and the ability to face business challenges. Good management of Intellectual Capital can have a positive impact on bank financial performance, by increasing efficiency and competitiveness (2) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR: CAR is a ratio that measures the adequacy of a bank's capital to withstand the risk of loss. A high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient capital to cover risks that may arise. At Bank Aceh Syariah, having adequate CAR is important to build customer trust and maintain financial stability. A high CAR can reflect the quality of bank assets, capital strength and the bank's ability to manage risk. A good CAR can improve a bank's financial performance and minimize the risk of loss (2) Non Performing Financing /NPF: NPF refers to financing that is not paid on time by the borrower. A high NPF level can indicate poor asset quality and increase the risk of losses. Therefore, Bank Aceh Syariah needs to manage its NPF well so that it does not have a negative impact on the bank's financial performance. Improving the quality of financing and careful monitoring of borrowers can help reduce NPF risk and improve financial performance (3) Return on Equity /ROE: ROE is a ratio that measures the level of return obtained by shareholders from their investment in the bank. High ROE indicates good efficiency and profitability. Bank Aceh Syariah needs to focus on increasing ROE by managing operational costs, increasing operational income, and optimizing capital use. A high ROE can attract investors and provide long-term profits for banks (4) Loan to Deposit Ratio /LDR: LDR is a ratio that measures the extent to which the bank uses customer savings funds to provide financing. A balanced LDR shows a balance between funding and financing. At Bank Aceh Syariah, maintaining a healthy LDR can minimize liquidity risk and maintain financial stability. A good LDR can also influence bank profitability and growth (5) Reserve for Impairment Losses/CKPN: CKPN is a reserve established by banks to anticipate losses due to decline in asset value. Adequate CKPN is important to protect banks from credit risks that may arise. At Bank Aceh Syariah, proper CKPN management can help maintain asset quality, reduce the risk of loss, and strengthen the bank's financial performance (6) Mudharabah Financing: Mudharabah financing is a type of financing used by Islamic banks. In the context of Bank Aceh Syariah's financial performance, Mudharabah financing can make a significant contribution to the bank's income and profitability. Good management of Mudharabah financing can improve bank financial performance by maximizing potential income and managing risks effectively (7) Operating Costs to Operating Income (BOPO): BOPO is a ratio that measures how efficient a bank is in managing its operational costs. The lower the BOPO, the more efficient the bank is in managing costs and increasing profitability. Bank Aceh Syariah needs to control its operational costs so as not to put excessive pressure on financial performance. Good operational efficiency can increase bank profitability and competitiveness in the market (Isnaliana, 2015).

Eleventh, analyze financial performance using the Sharia Conformity and Profitability (SCnP) Model, CAMEL (Capital, Asset, Management, Earning and Liquidity), RGEK (Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earning, Capital).

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Aceh Syariah Employee Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 20 topics related to the performance of Bank Aceh Syariah employees, namely:

First, understanding. Comprehension is the ability of employees to understand their duties and responsibilities well. In the context of Islamic banking, understanding sharia principles, sharia products and services offered, as well as internal regulations and policies is very important. If employees have good understanding, they can serve customers better, avoid mistakes, and improve service quality.

Second, customer introduction. Customer recognition is a bank's effort to identify and understand customer needs in depth. By getting to know customers well, employees can provide solutions and services that suit customer needs and preferences. This can increase customer satisfaction, foster better relationships, and increase customer loyalty towards Bank Aceh Syariah.

Third, supervision by the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS). DPS has an important role in supervising the operations of Bank Aceh Syariah so that they comply with sharia principles. The existence of DPS can give customers confidence that the products and services offered by the bank are in accordance with Islamic teachings. Employee performance can be influenced by their compliance with sharia rules and guidelines set by DPS.

Fourth, sources of work stress. Work stress can come from various factors, such as a heavy workload, pressure to achieve targets, or lack of support from the work environment. If employees at Bank Aceh Syariah face high sources of stress, this can affect their well-being and impact their performance. Good management needs to identify sources of stress and find ways to overcome or reduce them so that employees can work more effectively and productively.

Fifth, organizational culture. Organizational culture reflects the values, norms, and attitudes held by organizational members. If Bank Aceh Syariah has a culture that supports collaboration, innovation and fairness, employees tend to be more motivated and committed to delivering better results. Conversely, an unhealthy or unsupportive culture can negatively affect employee performance.

Sixth, work motivation. Work motivation refers to the internal drive that drives individuals to achieve goals, pursue achievements, and perform high. In the context of Bank Aceh Syariah, high work motivation among employees can have several positive impacts on their performance. Motivated employees tend to be more enthusiastic, have higher productivity, are more creative, and are more focused on achieving their work targets. High motivation is also closely related to improving the quality of service to customers, which contributes to the positive image of Bank Aceh Syariah in the eyes of customers.

Seventh, work environment. A conducive work environment is very important in improving employee performance. If Bank Aceh Syariah provides a positive, safe and supportive work environment, employees will feel more comfortable, satisfied and enthusiastic about working. A good work environment can also improve collaboration and communication between employees, facilitate the exchange of ideas, and improve work teams.

Conversely, a poor work environment can cause stress, tension, and conflict, which can have a negative impact on employee performance.

Eighth, organizational commitment. Organizational commitment refers to the extent to which employees feel bound and loyal to Bank Aceh Syariah as a place of work. Employees who have a high level of commitment tend to be more dedicated, have strong loyalty, and feel responsible for the success of Bank Aceh Syariah. High organizational commitment is also associated with better employee retention rates and reduced turnover, as employees tend to be more satisfied with their jobs and more invested in achieving organizational goals.

Ninth, Leader Member Exchange. Leader Member Exchange refers to the relationship between a leader and his team members. If Bank Aceh Syariah implements good LMX, where leaders treat employees fairly, provide support, and provide opportunities for career growth, then this can improve overall employee performance. Employees who feel appreciated and supported by leaders tend to be more motivated, have higher job satisfaction, and contribute actively to achieving organizational goals.

Tenth, work overload. Work overload or excessive workload can have a negative impact on employee performance. If employees at Bank Aceh Syariah experience a workload that is too heavy, they may experience physical and mental fatigue, stress, and even burnout. As a result, work quality and productivity can decrease. Apart from that, work overload can also affect employees' work-life balance and personal life, which in turn can affect employee absenteeism and retention levels.

Eleventh, intimidation. Intimidation is an action or behavior that frightens or causes fear in another person. If bullying occurs in the workplace, employees tend to feel insecure and stressed. This can lead to decreased productivity, low work motivation, and poor performance.

Twelfth, leadership style. Leadership style has a major impact on employee performance. An effective and inspirational leader tends to be able to motivate employees to achieve better performance. A leadership style that is participative and provides support will contribute to better employee performance compared to an authoritarian or less supportive style.

Thirteenth, career development. Career development is the process of improving employees' skills, knowledge and competencies to achieve their career goals. When Bank Aceh Syariah provides career development opportunities and programs to employees, this can increase employee motivation, sense of belonging and loyalty. Employees who feel appreciated and have opportunities to develop tend to perform better.

Fourth, fourteenth, Locus of Control. Locus of Control refers to a person's beliefs about the extent to which he feels he has control over his life. If employees have an internal Locus of Control, they tend to feel in control of their own performance and will try hard to achieve targets. This could have a positive impact on their performance at Bank Aceh Syariah.

Fifteenth, Islamic work ethics. In the Bank Aceh Syariah environment, Islamic work ethics play an important role. The principles of Islamic work ethics, such as trust, honesty, justice, and not accepting usury, can shape employee behavior that is responsible and has high integrity. Employees who adhere to strong Islamic work ethics can increase customer and company trust, as well as improve overall organizational performance.

Sixteenth, job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is a state where employees feel satisfied with their work and work environment. Job satisfaction can have a positive impact on employee performance, including at Bank Aceh Syariah.

When employees feel satisfied with their work, they tend to be more enthusiastic, motivated, and dedicated to achieving organizational goals. With job satisfaction, employees tend to be more productive, creative and take the initiative in carrying out their duties and responsibilities.

Seventeenth, compensation. Fair and competitive compensation or salary is an important factor in influencing employee performance. At Bank Aceh Syariah, providing appropriate compensation will encourage employees to work better. Good compensation can also increase employee motivation to achieve targets and better work results. In addition, adequate compensation also helps in retaining high-quality employees, thereby minimizing employee turnover rates and enabling Bank Aceh Syariah to maintain well-trained and experienced human resources.

Eighteenth, gratitude. Gratitude is a positive attitude expressed or shown by a company towards its employees for their contribution and good performance. Sincere gratitude from companies, including Bank Aceh Syariah, can increase employee loyalty and motivation. When employees feel appreciated and recognized for their efforts, they will feel more motivated to continue performing well and contribute more to the company's success.

Nineteenth, work engagement. Work engagement or " employee engagement " refers to the level of employee involvement, connectedness and commitment to their work and the company. A high level of work engagement can improve employee performance at Bank Aceh Syariah. Employees who feel connected to the company's vision and mission will try to achieve organizational goals with more enthusiasm. In addition, high work engagement is also associated with higher levels of job satisfaction and increased productivity.

Twentieth, education. Education is an important factor in improving the quality and performance of employees at Bank Aceh Syariah. Employees who have good education that is relevant to their work tend to have better knowledge and skills in carrying out their duties. Education also helps employees to keep up with the latest developments in the banking industry and provide more innovative solutions. Companies, including Bank Aceh Syariah, can provide opportunities for employees to take part in training and skills development so that they can continue to improve the quality of their performance.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Aceh Syariah Customer Behavior

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 4 topics related to Bank Aceh Syariah customer behavior, namely:

First, changes in sharia commercial banks regarding customers' interest in saving. There are several changes that have occurred in customers' interest in saving at Bank Aceh Syariah: (1)Awareness about Sharia Finance: Increasing public awareness about sharia finance has had a positive impact on interest in saving at Sharia banks, including Bank Aceh Syariah. More people are starting to understand the sharia principles that govern banking activities, including savings mechanisms that are more in line with Islamic financial principles (2)Development of Sharia Savings Products: Bank Aceh Syariah continues to develop sharia savings products that are attractive to customers. These products offer benefits in accordance with sharia principles, such as fair distribution of profits and do not contain interest elements. With the existence of savings products that are in line with Islamic financial values, customers' interest in saving at this bank increases (3)Sharia Financial Education: Bank Aceh Syariah actively provides educational programs about sharia finance to

customers and the general public. By increasing understanding of sharia products and principles, customers' interest in saving at Bank Aceh Syariah increases because they feel more confident and comfortable with the sharia approach implemented (4)Focus on Islamic Values: Bank Aceh Syariah also promotes Islamic values in all aspects of its operations. This includes an emphasis on business ethics, fairness and social responsibility, which can attract the interest of customers who wish to deposit their funds in financial institutions that adhere to religious principles.

Second, customer preferences in choosing financing products (public relations strategy, convenience, profits, security, product superiority, margin, income, financing procedures) (1)Public Relations Strategy : Bank Aceh Syariah adopts a strong public relations strategy to improve the public's image and trust in its services and products. In this effort, banks can use media, social campaigns, and participation in community events to build positive relationships with potential customers (2)Convenience and Benefits: Customers tend to choose financing products that offer convenience in the application process and requirements that are not too complicated. Apart from that, competitive and fair profits in accordance with sharia principles will be an important consideration for customers in choosing financing products at Bank Aceh Syariah (3)Security: Bank Aceh Syariah must demonstrate commitment to the security of customer funds. In the sharia banking system, financing products are often based on agreements or contracts that comply with Islamic law. Demonstrating security in preparing contracts and managing funds will provide more confidence for customers (4)Product Advantages: Bank Aceh Syariah must identify the advantages of its financing products compared to other banks. These advantages may include more flexible terms, a faster application process, or a more competitive profit level compared to competitors (5)Margins and Income: Competitive margins and fair income for banks and customers are significant factors in selecting financing products. Margin calculations that comply with sharia principles and provide benefits for both parties will attract customer interest (6)Transparent Financing Procedures: Bank Aceh Syariah must show transparency in its financing procedures, explaining in detail the customer's rights and obligations in the financing contract. This transparency will help customers better understand the financing products they choose.

Third, customer preferences in choosing savings products (service quality, profit sharing, income level, religiosity, product quality, risks, benefits, convenience, knowledge, location, social environment, sharia values, perceptions, attitudes, beliefs, product information). The following are several factors that customers consider when choosing savings products at Bank Aceh Syariah: (1)Service Quality: Customers want friendly, fast and responsive service from bank staff. Good service quality will increase customer satisfaction (2)Profit Sharing: Savings products in sharia banks are based on the principle of profit sharing (mudharabah). Customers will consider the level of profit obtained from the savings product (3)Income level: The customer's economic condition will influence their preferences in choosing savings products. Products that are suitable for customers with low incomes may be different from those for customers with high incomes (4)Religiosity: Religious factors also influence customer preferences in choosing savings products. Bank Aceh Syariah, as a sharia bank, offers products that comply with Islamic sharia principles (5)Product Quality: Customers will consider savings product features, such as cash withdrawal facilities, transfers, ATM cards, and others (6)Risk:

Customers will see the risk level of the savings products offered, including liquidity risk and investment value (7)Benefits: Savings products with additional benefits such as insurance or shopping discounts can attract customers' interest (8)Convenience: The ease of carrying out transactions and administering savings also influences customer preferences (9)Knowledge: The customer's level of understanding about savings products will influence their choice (10)Location: Ease of access to Bank Aceh Syariah branch offices or ATMs can also be a consideration for customers (11)Social Environment: Influence from family, friends, or the surrounding social environment can also influence customer preferences (12)Sharia Values: Customers who care about compliance with sharia principles will prefer savings products from sharia banks (13)Perception, Attitude and Trust: The image and reputation of Bank Aceh Syariah will influence customers' views of its products and services (14)Product Information: The availability of clear and easy to understand information about savings products will help customers in making decisions.

Fourth, use of Mobile Banking. Mobile banking is a banking service that allows customers to carry out various banking transactions via mobile devices, such as smartphones or tablets. Using mobile banking provides several benefits, including: (1)Ease of Access: Customers can access their accounts anytime and anywhere without having to come to a physical branch office (2)Easy Transactions: Through mobile banking, customers can transfer funds, pay bills, purchase credit and other banking activities quickly and easily (3)Security: Mobile banking is generally equipped with layers of security, such as the use of a PIN, fingerprint, or two-factor authentication, so that transactions are more secure (4)Real - time Notifications and Information : Customers can get direct notifications and information regarding their account activities (5)Time Savings: With mobile banking, customers do not need to queue at branch offices or ATMs to make transactions (6)Additional Features: Some banks provide additional features in mobile banking, such as transaction graphs, personal financial management, and product recommendations.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues in Bank Aceh Syariah

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 10 research topics related to issues at Bank Aceh Syariah, namely:

First, issuing a bank guarantee to guarantee construction service users. As a sharia bank, Bank Aceh Syariah can issue bank guarantees for users of construction services. A bank guarantee is a financial instrument that functions to provide payment guarantees to the guarantee recipient (the party receiving construction services)if the guaranteed party (the contractor)cannot fulfill its obligations according to the contract. By issuing a bank guarantee, Bank Aceh Syariah acts as a guarantee party to ensure that payments to users of construction services can be made if there is a default on the part of the contractor.

Second, legal protection for creditors. Bank Aceh Syariah, like other banks, must provide legal protection for creditors. This means that banks must ensure that providing credit or financing to customers is carried out using a process that complies with applicable statutory provisions. Apart from that, if there is a customer's inability to repay credit or financing, the bank must also protect its rights as a creditor in the receivable settlement process.

Third, implementation of Good Corporate Governance (GCG). Good Corporate Governance (GCG)refers to the principles of good corporate

governance. Bank Aceh Syariah is expected to implement GCG to maintain integrity, transparency, accountability and fairness in managing the bank. Implementing GCG will help banks to carry out their activities efficiently and effectively, protecting the interests of all stakeholders, including customers, shareholders, employees and the community.

Fourth, managing passive customer accounts. Passive accounts are a type of account that collects funds from customers through savings products such as savings and deposits. Bank Aceh Syariah is responsible for managing customers' passive accounts carefully and trustfully. This includes providing clear information to customers about products and applicable conditions, managing customer funds well to provide a reasonable level of profit in accordance with sharia principles, and providing good service to customers so that they feel satisfied with the management of their accounts.

Fifth, the influence of Murabahah, Musyarakah, Corporate Social Responsibility / CSR financing on improving community welfare, Return On Assets / ROA (1)Murabahah financing contributes to improving community welfare by facilitating access to goods or other needs that may be difficult for the community to purchase in cash. With Murabahah financing, people can obtain these needs with a payment system that is more flexible and in accordance with sharia principles (2)Musyarakah financing can have a positive impact on improving community welfare because it involves active participation from the parties involved. The profits obtained will be shared fairly according to the agreement, thereby helping to reduce economic disparities and increase purchasing power and overall community welfare (3)By carrying out CSR activities, Bank Aceh Syariah can help improve community welfare through various programs such as education, health, environment and community economic empowerment. Through CSR, banks can create a positive impact in the communities they serve, increase public trust, and strengthen the company's positive image (4)Appropriate implementation of Murabahah and Musyarakah financing, as well as commitment to implementing CSR, can have a positive impact on the ROA of Bank Aceh Syariah. Sharia financing that is in accordance with sharia principles can attract more customers, while effective CSR activities can increase the trust of customers and society as a whole, which in turn can increase Bank Aceh Syariah's profits and ROA.

Sixth, implementation of Salam contract financing. Bank Aceh Syariah implements financing with a Salam contract, which is a form of sharia financing. A Salam contract is a sale and purchase transaction in which the customer pays a sum of money in advance to obtain goods or products that will be sent by the bank at a specified time in the future. In financing Salam contracts, the bank acts as a seller who receives payment in advance, and then provides the product or goods purchased by the customer at the agreed time.

Seventh, the influence of Bank Aceh Syariah on the development of halal tourism. Bank Aceh Syariah plays a role in supporting and developing the halal tourism sector in its region. Halal tourism is a form of tourism that is based on sharia principles, where the facilities and services meet sharia requirements, such as not serving alcoholic drinks, providing halal food, and respecting Islamic customs. Bank Aceh Syariah can provide financing and support to local entrepreneurs or companies operating in the halal tourism sector, such as hotels and restaurants that offer halal food, family recreation centers that comply with Islamic values, and the like. Through distributed financing, Bank Aceh Syariah can help improve infrastructure and service quality in the halal

tourism sector, thereby contributing to the growth of the tourism industry in accordance with sharia principles in the region.

Eighth, Hajj funds (management, Hajj savings with a wadiah agreement). Bank Aceh Syariah can provide Hajj savings services using a wadiah contract. A wadiah contract is a form of savings and loan agreement in which the customer entrusts funds (savings) to the bank, and the bank acts as the trust manager of these funds. In the case of Hajj savings, funds deposited by customers will be managed by the bank carefully and used for Hajj purposes in accordance with applicable regulations. The management of Hajj funds by Bank Aceh Syariah is carried out in compliance with sharia principles, and the bank does not use these funds for business or investment purposes which are contrary to Islamic law. So, customers who are saving for the Hajj can entrust their funds to Bank Aceh Syariah with the confidence that these funds are managed with the principles of prudence and sharia compliance.

Ninth, non-halal income. As a sharia bank, Bank Aceh Syariah is committed to avoiding income from non-halal sources, namely income originating from activities or businesses that are prohibited or contrary to Islamic sharia principles. Examples of non-halal income that sharia banks avoid are income from interest or usury, gambling, alcoholic drinks, non-halal food, and the like. Bank Aceh Syariah aims to ensure that all income it obtains is from transactions and businesses that comply with sharia principles, such as financing with valid contracts, halal investments, and other sharia-based financial services. By avoiding non-halal income, Bank Aceh Syariah can maintain integrity and compliance with Islamic values in its operations and business activities.

Tenth, the influence of Bank Aceh Syariah on the growth of MSMEs. Bank Aceh Syariah plays an important role in supporting the growth of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in its region. MSMEs have a strategic role in the economy, and Islamic banks understand the importance of developing the MSME sector in accordance with sharia principles. Bank Aceh Syariah can provide sharia financing to MSMEs to support operational activities, business expansion, procurement of working capital, and product or service development. Apart from that, banks can also provide guidance and consultation to MSME entrepreneurs to improve the quality and competitiveness of their products.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 4 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Bank Aceh Syariah, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; and (4) Other issues.

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